

VALIDATION QUESTIONNAIRE

Evaluation of the Domain Knowledge Acquisition Approach

Purpose of the Instrument

This questionnaire aims to evaluate:

- The quality of the acquired knowledge (correctness and completeness);
- The effort required to apply the proposed approach;
- The acceptance of the approach based on the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM).

* Indicates required question

Part 1 - Knowledge Correctness

Please assess the conceptual accuracy and semantic adequacy of the represented knowledge.

1. 1. The identified concepts are semantically correct. *

Mark only one oval.

- Strongly disagree
- Partially disagree
- Neither agree nor disagree
- Partially agree
- Strongly agree

2. 2. The definitions assigned to the concepts are appropriate for the domain. *

Mark only one oval.

- Strongly disagree
- Partially disagree
- Neither agree nor disagree
- Partially agree
- Strongly agree

3. 3. The relationships established between concepts are correct. *

Mark only one oval.

- Strongly disagree
- Partially disagree
- Neither agree nor disagree
- Partially agree
- Strongly agree

4. 4. I did not identify relevant conceptual inconsistencies. *

Mark only one oval.

- Strongly disagree
- Partially disagree
- Neither agree nor disagree
- Partially agree
- Strongly agree

5. 5. The represented knowledge is technically aligned with real-world domain practice. *

Mark only one oval.

- Strongly disagree
- Partially disagree
- Neither agree nor disagree
- Partially agree
- Strongly agree

6. 6. The terminology used is appropriate. *

Mark only one oval.

- Strongly disagree
- Partially disagree
- Neither agree nor disagree
- Partially agree
- Strongly agree

7. 7. Please identify any incorrect or inadequately represented concepts.

8. 8. Please indicate any relationships that should be corrected or removed.

Part 2 - Knowledge Completeness

Please assess the coverage and comprehensiveness of the represented knowledge.

9. 1. The main domain concepts covered to a level that can be considered satisfactory. *

Mark only one oval.

- Strongly disagree
- Partially disagree
- Neither agree nor disagree
- Partially agree
- Strongly agree

10. 2. The essential relationships between concepts are represented. *

Mark only one oval.

- Strongly disagree
- Partially disagree
- Neither agree nor disagree
- Partially agree
- Strongly agree

11. 3. I did not identify relevant knowledge gaps. *

Mark only one oval.

- Strongly disagree
- Partially disagree
- Neither agree nor disagree
- Partially agree
- Strongly agree

12. 4. The representation allows a clear understanding of the domain's overall structure. *

Mark only one oval.

- Strongly disagree
- Partially disagree
- Neither agree nor disagree
- Partially agree
- Strongly agree

13. 5. Which important concepts were not included?

14. 6. Which relationships should be considered?

15. 7. Which aspects are superficial and should be further detailed?

Part 3 - Application Effort

Please evaluate the effort required to apply the proposed approach.

16. 1. The approach reduced the time required to structure domain knowledge. *

Mark only one oval.

- Strongly disagree
- Partially disagree
- Neither agree nor disagree
- Partially agree
- Strongly agree

17. 2. The approach reduced overall cognitive effort. *

Mark only one oval.

- Strongly disagree
- Partially disagree
- Neither agree nor disagree
- Partially agree
- Strongly agree

18. 3. The identification of concepts was facilitated. *

Mark only one oval.

- Strongly disagree
- Partially disagree
- Neither agree nor disagree
- Partially agree
- Strongly agree

19. 4. The identification of relationships was facilitated. *

Mark only one oval.

- Strongly disagree
- Partially disagree
- Neither agree nor disagree
- Partially agree
- Strongly agree

20. 5. The validation of knowledge was facilitated. *

Mark only one oval.

- Strongly disagree
- Partially disagree
- Neither agree nor disagree
- Partially agree
- Strongly agree

21. 6. Compared to a traditional approach, the application was less demanding. *

Mark only one oval.

- Strongly disagree
- Partially disagree
- Neither agree nor disagree
- Partially agree
- Strongly agree

22. 7. The tools were easy to use. *

Mark only one oval.

- Strongly disagree
- Partially disagree
- Neither agree nor disagree
- Partially agree
- Strongly agree

23. 8. The application required substantial manual effort. *

Mark only one oval.

- Strongly disagree
- Partially disagree
- Neither agree nor disagree
- Partially agree
- Strongly agree

24. 9. Which steps required the greatest effort?

25. 10. What could be improved to further reduce effort?

Part 4 - Acceptance of the Approach

26. 1. The approach improves the quality of the process of acquired knowledge. *

Mark only one oval.

- Strongly disagree
- Partially disagree
- Neither agree nor disagree
- Partially agree
- Strongly agree

27. 2. The approach contributes to better knowledge organization. *

Mark only one oval.

- Strongly disagree
- Partially disagree
- Neither agree nor disagree
- Partially agree
- Strongly agree

28. 3. The approach facilitates knowledge acquired validation. *

Mark only one oval.

- Strongly disagree
- Partially disagree
- Neither agree nor disagree
- Partially agree
- Strongly agree

29. 4. I would use this approach in real-world activities. *

Mark only one oval.

- Strongly disagree
- Partially disagree
- Neither agree nor disagree
- Partially agree
- Strongly agree

30. 5. I would recommend this approach to other professionals. *

Mark only one oval.

- Strongly disagree
- Partially disagree
- Neither agree nor disagree
- Partially agree
- Strongly agree

Part 6 - Overall Evaluation

31. Overall, I evaluate the approach as:

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Very Very positive

32. Final comments about the approach:

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